

Base-cases definitions and KPI calculation for cement, steel, Bio-CHP and WtE plants with and without capture

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1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable presents the techno-economic analysis of reference Calcium-Looping (CaL) systems based on circulating fluidized bed (CFB) reactors integrated in the CaLBy2030 target industrial sectors. The first part of deliverable D4.3 provides a description of the reference plants, the methodology and the definition of the various key performance indicators (KPIs) considered for energy, technical and economic comparisons. In order to have a complete overview of the impact of CaLby2030 technologies on host plants, it was also chosen to analyze the case when the four references systems are integrated with conventional MEA-based CO₂ capture units. The integration of the various reference plants with a MEA-based CO₂ capture system is then described. In the last part of the deliverable, the reference CaL-based plants are presented. Both CO₂ capture technologies analyzed in this report have been integrated into the four host plants in a retrofit fashion.

2 DESCRIPTION OF REFERENCE PLANTS

This section describes the reference cement, waste-to-energy, bio-CHP and steel plants in which the reference MEA and CaL CO₂ capture systems are then integrated in Sections 4 and 5.

2.1 Reference cement plant

The reference cement plant without CO₂ capture relies on the Best Available Technique (BAT) defined in the European BREF-Documents (Best Available Technique Reference) for the manufacture of cement (Schorcht et al., 2013). In this reference configuration, illustrated in Figure 1, the cement kiln consists of a one-string five-stage cyclone preheater, a pre-calciner with a tertiary air duct, a rotary kiln and a grate clinker cooler. The reference cement plant model was developed in the framework of the CEMCAP project (Anantharaman et al., 2018; Campanari et al., 2016). The production capacity of the reference cement kiln is about 2825 t_{clinker}/day (raw meal/clinker factor 1.6), which is a representative size for a European cement plant. This size corresponds to a clinker production of 1 Mt per year (equivalent for a run time of >330 days/year) and a cement production of 1.36 Mt per year, assuming an average clinker/cement factor of 0.737. Considering a capacity factor of 91.5%, the annual CO₂ emitted at the stack by this plant without CCS is around 800 kt_{CO2}/y.

Figure 1: Schematic of the reference cement burning process without CCS.

As depicted in Figure 1, the raw materials are grounded and dried via the direct contact with the hot gases coming from the preheater tower. The dried raw meal, with the composition given in Table 1, is heated up in a five-stage cyclone preheater by direct contact with the process gases that pass through the preheater in a counter-flow arrangement. Each stage of the preheater is composed of a riser duct, where the solid particles are entrained upwards and heated up by the gas, and a cyclone, which separates the particles and distributes them to the underlying stage. Cyclone efficiencies, heat losses and air in-leakages are reported in Table 2. The dusty gases used in the drying and grinding processes in the raw mill, are separated from the entrained solids by means of a cyclone and a fabric filter and then sent to the stack. Electric consumptions of the fans, placed in the gas clean-up line, are included in the overall specific electric consumption of the clinker production process (including also raw mill, clinker cooler fans, etc.), that results to be $131.6 \text{ kWh}_e/t_{\text{clik}}$ (corresponding to $97 \text{ kWh}_e/t_{\text{cem}}$ if referred to the units of cement produced).

Table 1: Raw meal composition (wt.%), after drying.

Species	Mass composition, %
CaCO ₃	79.08
SiO ₂	13.77
Al ₂ O ₃	3.33
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.01
MgCO ₃	1.53
Moisture	0.28

Table 2: Main parameters considered for the reference clinker production process.

Parameters	
Reference fuel mix	100% coal
Ambient temperature, °C	15.0
Clinker production, tpd	2825
Clinker/cement factor, -	0.737
Overall specific electric consumption, kWh _e /t _{cem}	97
Cyclones efficiency (1 st /2 nd /3 rd /4 th stage), %	96/86/86/86
Pre-calciner cyclone efficiency, %	75.6
Primary and transport air to pre-calciner, Nm ³ /kg _{coal} to precalciner	0.24
Primary and transport air to rotary kiln, Nm ³ / kg _{coal} to rotary kiln	1.74
Secondary air to rotary kiln, Nm ³ /t _{clk}	259.7
Tertiary air to pre-calciner, Nm ³ /t _{clk}	622.4
Coal input to rotary kiln, kJ _{LHV} /kg _{clk}	1210
Pre-calciner outlet temperature, °C	861.8
Parameters	
Rotary kiln gas outlet temperature, °C	1078.5
Secondary air temperature, °C	1137.0
Tertiary air temperature, °C	1049.8
Clinker temperature at cooler outlet, °C	114.9
Temperature of solids after milling, °C	60.0
Calcination degree at pre-calciner outlet, %	94.2
Heat losses from rotary kiln, kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	180.2
Heat losses from pre-calciner, kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	95.64
Heat losses from clinker cooler, kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	11.13
Heat losses from preheater tower, kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	19.02
Air in-leakages into rotary kiln, Nm ³ /t _{clk}	11.98
Air in-leakages into pre-calciner, Nm ³ /t _{clk}	6.4
Air in-leakages into pre-calciner cyclone, Nm ³ /t _{clk}	6.4
Air in-leakages into preheater tower (1 st /2 nd /3 rd /4 th stage), Nm ³ /t _{clk}	18.8/9.4/9.4/9.4

The preheated raw materials are fed to the pre-calciner, where most of the CaCO₃ and MgCO₃ are calcined into CaO, MgO and CO₂, with a calcination degree (defined as the ratio between the moles of CaO and the total moles of Ca at calciner outlet) of about 94%. The thermal energy needed for the calcination reaction is provided by combustion of coal, whose composition and lower heating value are reported in Table 3. Coal is fed to the pre-calciner by a pneumatic transport system using air at ambient temperature as transport gas. Tertiary air (III air) from the clinker cooler at 1050°C is used for combustion in the pre-calciner. An in-line calciner configuration is considered, meaning that the kiln off-gas at 1078 °C is fed into the pre-calciner.

Table 3: Coal composition (wt.%) and heating value

Species	
C	69.00
H	4.00
S	0.50
N	0.48
O	9.00
Ash	16.50
Moisture	0.50
Lower Heating Value, MJ/kg	27.15

Ash composition, %wt.	
SiO ₂	43.70
Al ₂ O ₃	32.42
CaO	18.18
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.00
MgO	1.70

The rotary kiln represents the core of the clinker production process, where the completion of the calcination and the formation of the clinker constituents occur. The hot clinker moves towards the hot end of the reactor, where coal combustion occurs. Air for combustion in the rotary kiln comes from the clinker cooler (II Air), from the primary and the fuel transport air. After the combustion zone, the flue gas moves towards the pre-calciner, in counter-current fashion with respect to the solids. As the solid phase moves towards the rotary kiln burner, the clinker phases are formed. Temperature of about 1450°C is reached by the hot clinker at the end of the kiln, before being discharged to the clinker cooler.

In the clinker cooler, clinker is rapidly cooled down to minimize the formation of undesired coarse crystals and preventing the dissociation of alite (C3S, 3CaO·SiO₂) into belite (C2S, 2CaO·SiO₂) and free lime (CaO). Each main clinker phase is modelled according to a Bogue approach which is thought to be reasonably accurate to represent the heat and mass balances of the cement kiln. Detailed mineralogical phase composition and distribution is not simulated by this model, since it is a chemical equilibrium based model without kinetics. Ambient air is used as cooling medium in the clinker cooler. Most of this air is heated up to over 1000 °C and used as secondary and tertiary combustion air in the rotary kiln and the pre-calciner, respectively. A stream of air at lower temperature (~300°C) is generated in the final part of the clinker cooler, which is ultimately vented to the atmosphere after filtration.

In Table 4, the global results calculated for the reference cement kiln process are shown.

Table 4: Global parameters of reference cement plant.

Cement plant global balance	
Clinker, tpd	2824
Total fuel input, kg/s	3.90
Total heat input, MW _{LHV}	105.95
Fuel to kiln, % of total	38.0
Specific heat input, MJ _{LHV} /kg _{clik}	3.24
Fuel consumption in the rotary kiln, MJ _{LHV} /kg _{clik}	1.23
Fuel consumption in the pre-calciner, MJ _{LHV} /kg _{clik}	2.01
Specific electric consumption, kWh _e /t _{clik}	131.6
Specific CO ₂ emissions at stack, g _{CO2} /kg _{clik}	864.7

2.2 Waste to Energy and Bio-CHP reference plants

The reference Waste-to-Energy (WtE) plant considered in this deliverable refers to a generic modern European WtE as described in the BAT report (Neuwahl et al., 2019). The plant provides electricity and thermal heat through the city's district heating network to the nearby metropolitan area. A schematic of the WtE plant is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic of WtE plant with district heating

The plant is composed of two grate-based combustion lines, each with its own dedicated flue-gas treatment section, treating a total of 700 kt of municipal solid waste (MSW) per year. The two grate boilers are designed for a thermal power of 121.5 MW_{th} each, corresponding to an hourly throughput of about 43.75 t/h of MSW. The plant is expected to operate for 8000 equivalent hours per year, corresponding to a capacity factor of 91.3%. The properties of the design waste are resumed in Table 5.

Table 5: Properties of the design MSW of the reference WtE.

MSW composition		
C – Carbon	wt%	26.42%
H – Hydrogen	wt%	3.68%
N – Nitrogen	wt%	0.47%
O – Oxygen	wt%	19.05%
S – Sulphur	wt%	0.16%
Cl – Chlorine	wt%	0.45%
Ash	wt%	16.00%
Humidity	wt%	33.76%
LHV – Lower Heating Value	MJ/kg	10.00

The heat released during the combustion process is recovered under the form of superheated steam, to be valorized in the steam cycle of the plant, featuring a steam turbine with nominal gross electric power of 78 MW_e and operating

at turbine inlet conditions of 425°C and 50 bar (Neuwahl et al., 2019). The condensing pressure is assumed to be 0.085 bar. The flue gas treatment (FGT) line is designed to meet the specifications highlighted in the BAT report and, in particular, the Table 6 reports the range of the main pollutants in the flue gas at stack.

Table 6: Range of pollutants in the flue gas, as reported in (Neuwahl et al., 2019).

Dust	mg/Nm ³ - daily average	< 2 - 5
Cd + Tl	mg/Nm ³ - average over the sampling period	0.005 - 0.02
Sb+As+Pb+Cr+Co+Cu+Mn+Ni+V	mg/Nm ³ - average over the sampling period	0.01 - 0.3
HCl	mg/Nm ³ - daily average	< 2 - 6
HF	mg/Nm ³ - daily average	< 1
SO ₂	mg/Nm ³ - daily average	5 - 30
NO _x	mg/Nm ³ - daily average	50 - 120
CO	mg/Nm ³ - daily average	10 - 50
NH ₃	mg/Nm ³ - daily average	2 - 10
TVOC	mg/Nm ³ - daily average	< 3 - 10
Hg	µg/Nm ³ - long-term sampling period	1 - 10

The flow rate, temperature and content of the main constituents of the WtE flue gas at stack are reported in Table 7.

Table 7: WtE plant flue gas characteristics

Flue gas outlet	m ³ /h STP	235'364
Flue gas outlet	m ³ /h STP dry 11% O ₂	260'041
Temperature at stack	°C	120
N ₂	%vol - wet	63.2%
O ₂	%vol - wet	6.4%
CO ₂	%vol - wet	9.2%
H ₂ O	%vol - wet	21.2%

The **Bio-CHP** plant taken as reference in this project is managed by Grupo HUNOSA and is a CFB-based combustion boiler originally deputed to burn locally sourced coal, later adapted to accept waste biomass co-combustion and now undergoing a retrofit to accept 100% biomass feed. The properties of the wood pellet that will be burnt in the plant are reported in Table 8. The fuel requirements make it compatible with the ENplus A1 category. Also for the Bio-CHP plant, 8000 equivalent working hours per year have been assumed.

Table 8: Wood pellet properties for the bio-CHP case.

Wood pellet composition		
C – Carbon	wt%	48.80%
H – Hydrogen	wt%	5.70%
N – Nitrogen	wt%	0.06%
O – Oxygen	wt%	41.20%
S – Sulphur	wt%	0.008%
Cl – Chlorine	wt%	0.006%
Ash	wt%	0.40 %
Humidity	wt%	3.80%
LHV – Lower Heating Value	MJ/kg	18.54

The properties of the flue gases at the stack are reported in Table 9.

Table 9: Bio CHP plant flue gas attributes and composition at stack (Ar is lumped into N₂).

Flue gas outlet	Nm ³ /h (1.013 bar, 0°C)	138'096
Temperature	°C	150
N ₂	%vol, wet basis	70.20%
O ₂	%vol, wet basis	5.0%
CO ₂	%vol, wet basis	13.05%
H ₂ O	%vol, wet basis	11.75%

In Table 10 the main performance of both WtE and Bio-CHP reference plants are reported.

Table 10: WtE and Bio-CHP KPIs for full electric operating mode

		WtE	Bio-CHP
Type of fuel	-	Municipal Solid Waste	Wood pellet
Nominal thermal input	MW _{th}	243.1	135.3
Fuel consumption	t/y – TJ _{LHV} /y	700'000 – 7'000	210'000 – 3'896
Gross electricity production	MW – MWh/y	77.0 – 616'000	43.4 – 347'000
Gross electric efficiency	%	31.68%	32.08%
Net electricity production	MW – MWh/y	70.0 – 560'000	39.1 – 313'000
Net electric efficiency	%	28.80%	28.90%
CO ₂ emissions	t/y – kg/t _{fuel} – kg/GJ _{fuel}	673'000 – 961.90 – 96.19	282'000 – 1'343 – 72.38

2.3 Reference steel plant

The system considered as the reference plant for the Steel case is an Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) owned by Celsa Nordic and located in Mo i Rana, Norway. It is a Tenova consteel EAF with a nominal capacity of 112 ton/h of steel. In the general EAF process, the feedstock (mainly scrap) is melted at elevated temperatures (1700-1800°C) by the supply of electricity through electrodes. The nominal consumptions of the plant are reported in Table 11.

Table 11. Reference EAF feed, electricity, and anthracite consumption (information about scrap and fuel consumption was not available).

Carbon addition (anthracite)	8 kg/ton _{steel}
Electrode consumption	5 kg/ton _{steel}
Oxygen	3000 – 5000 Nm ³ /h
Electricity	50 – 70 MW
Calcium oxide	22.6 kg/ton steel
Dolomite	17.8 kg/ton steel

The flue gases properties considered for this work were measured at the plant. The schematic diagram of the system, indicating the measurement points, is presented in Figure 3. The measurements were made at different positions. At position 1, located in the scrap pre-heating duct, the gas temperature and contents of CO, CO₂, H₂, and O₂ were measured. Volume flow rate and dust load were measured at position 2 after the post-combustion zone; while the properties measured at position 3 were gas temperature and contents of H₂O, CO, CO₂, O₂, NH₃, NO_x, CH₄, etc. The ranges for each property and average values are reported in Table 12.

Figure 3. Schematic of the EAF plant with the location of measurement points.

Table 12. Ranges and average value for the flue gas properties measured at the EAF plant.

Position 1	Range	Average
CO, ppm	0.03 – 10'197	392
CO ₂ , %vol, wet basis	0.01 – 25.44	7.11
H ₂ , %vol, wet basis	0.00 – 4.17	0.25
O ₂ , %vol, wet basis	0.67 – 21.49	14.67
Temperature, °C	250 – 1197	678
Position 2	Range	Average
Volume flow rate, Nm ³ /h	1'954– 356'798	151'391
Position3	Range	Average
CO, ppm	0.11 – 7303.96	447.41
CO ₂ , %vol, wet basis	0.08 – 10.00	3.02
H ₂ O, %vol, wet basis	0.52 – 12.90	4.27
O ₂ , %vol, wet basis	11.11 – 23.16	17.37
N ₂ O, ppm	0.0 – 1.76	0.24
NO, ppm	0.01 – 351.43	18.52
NO ₂ , ppm	0.01 – 17.68	1.66
NH ₃ , ppm	0.06 – 17.49	4.21
SO ₂ , ppm	0.03 – 117.43	4.27
SO ₃ , ppm	0.01 – 1.08	0.24
HCl, ppm	0.01 – 4.49	0.52
HF, ppm	1.37 – 53.06	10.00
HCN, ppm	0.01 – 13.65	2.50
CH ₄ , ppm	0.01 – 195.86	12.06
C ₂ H ₆ , ppm	0.01 – 20.41	3.04
C ₂ H ₄ , ppm	0.01 – 445.25	8.64
C ₃ H ₈ , ppm	0.01 – 3.93	0.63
C ₆ H ₁₄ , ppm	0.10 – 11.24	2.85
CHOH, ppm	0.02 – 33.85	7.26
Temperature, °C	100.00 – 421.50	230.21

For the steel case, the CO₂ capture system (i.e., CaL or MEA) is placed between the post-combustion section and the air cooler (see Figure 3). Even though placing the capture system right after the EAF (i.e., point 1) would result in a better performance of the capture process due to a lower gas flow rate and higher CO₂ concentration, it would require significant retrofitting of the current steelmaking plant, which is not considered in the definition of the base case.

Nonetheless, a comparative analysis is required to identify the best configuration from a technoeconomic point of view. The flue gas properties considered are the volume flow rate measured at point 2 and the composition and temperature measured at point 3, whose profiles and distributions are presented in Figure 4. These profiles resulted from the processed dataset after removal of unreliable values (related to problems during measurements) and last for 962 minutes. The flue gases from the EAF have highly fluctuating properties and with a cyclic behavior in which they first increase from minimum values to a peak, and then decrease again to minimum values in periods ranging from 40 to 57 minutes.

Figure 4: Profiles and distribution (max, average and min values) of a) Volume flow rate, b) CO₂, O₂, and H₂O concentrations, and temperature of flue gases from the EAF plant measured at point 3 (see Figure 3)

For the definition of the base cases for steel (CaL ad MEA), the analysis is carried out by considering a set of six representative operating conditions, according to the profiles in Figure 4, which are presented in Table 13. Then, the capture system (CaL or MEA) is designed based on the most critical conditions with the highest flow rate and CO₂ concentration(A), whereas the operation under different conditions is analysed as off-design cases (B-F).

Table 13: Volume flow rate, composition, and temperature of flue gases considered.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
Criteria	Percentile 95	Percentile 75	Percentile 50	Percentile 25	**	Percentile 0
Volume flow rate, Nm ³ /h	298'581	231'691	155'229	75'672	30'564	6'482
Temperature, °C	324	287	248	202	177	106
X _{CO₂} , %vol	5.91	4.54	3.20	1.88	1.38	0.19
X _{O₂} , %vol	14.56	15.73	16.94	18.40	18.99	20.60
X _{H₂O} , %vol	6.55	5.92	5.12	3.71	2.90	0.66
X _{N₂} , %vol [†]	72.98	73.81	74.74	76.01	76.73	78.54

[†]By difference, not measured.

** Case E represents the lowest off-gas flow rate to have a minimum fluidization velocity of 0.5 m/s in the carbonator of the CaL system. This is the boundary below which air injection into the carbonator is required.

The authors would like to thank SWERIM, Sumitomo SHI FW and Celsa Nordic for their contribution to the site measurements that led to the EAF flue gas data used in this deliverable.

3 METHODOLOGY AND KPIS

The simulations of the integration of the different CO₂ capture technologies (MEA and CaL) and of the CO₂ compression and purification unit (CPU) have been done using the commercial software Aspen Plus v11 and the in-house software GS (GECOS, 2016). The performance of the carbonator (in terms of CO₂ removal efficiency) has been estimated using a MATLAB model based on (Romano, 2012). The estimation of CaL-based plant costs has been made using cost functions for each equipment and reported in (CEMCAP, 2018a; De Lena et al., 2019; Gardarsdottir et al., 2019), or by reproducing the various plant sections in THERMOFLEX v31, discounting the costs using the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index (CEPCI), in order to bring all the costs at the same basis (i.e. EUR 2023). Regarding the equipment cost for the MEA cases, some recently published references (Martorell et al., 2023) and reports from the National Energy Technology Laboratory (Hughes et al., 2022) have been adopted for the evaluation of the equipment cost of key components (e.g. packed columns, heat exchangers and compressors).

The following sections present the various energy and techno-economic KPIS used in this deliverable to compare the different processes.

3.1 Technical KPIS

The plant performances have been evaluated with KPIS that are common to all the CO₂ capture technologies applied to the different case studies, with the aim of making them easily comparable.

- Gross electric efficiency (only for WtE and Bio-CHP cases)

$$\eta_{gross} [\%] = \frac{\dot{P}_{el,gross}}{\dot{m}_{fuel} \cdot LHV}$$

Where $\dot{P}_{el,gross}$ is the gross electric power of the plant, \dot{m}_{fuel} the mass flow rate of fuel and LHV the Lower Heating Value of the fuel.

- Net electric efficiency (only for WtE and Bio-CHP cases)

$$\eta_{met} [\%] = \frac{\dot{P}_{el,gross} - \sum \dot{P}_{el,aux.}}{\dot{m}_{fuel} \cdot LHV}$$

Where $\sum \dot{P}_{el,aux.}$ is the sum of all the electrical auxiliaries of the plant.

- Direct specific primary energy consumption (only for cement and steel -making cases)

$$q_{dir,clk \text{ or } steel} \left[\frac{MJ_{LHV}}{t_{clk \text{ or } steel}} \right] = \frac{\dot{m}_{fuel} \cdot LHV}{\dot{m}_{clk \text{ or } steel}}$$

Where $\dot{m}_{clk \text{ or } steel}$ is the mass flow rate of clinker or steel produced in the plant.

- Indirect specific primary energy consumption associated to electricity consumptions (only for cement and steel -making cases)

$$q_{indir,clk \text{ or } steel} \left[\frac{MJ_{LHV}}{t_{clk \text{ or } steel}} \right] = \frac{\dot{P}_{el}/\eta_{el,ref}}{\dot{m}_{clk \text{ or } steel}}$$

Where $\eta_{el,ref}$ is the EU-27 electrical efficiency in the year 2022, equal to 51.3%, as reported in EUROSTAT database (Eurostat, 2022).

- Equivalent specific primary energy consumption (only for cement and steel -making cases)

$$q_{eq,clk \text{ or } steel} \left[\frac{MJ_{LHV}}{t_{clk \text{ or } steel}} \right] = q_{dir,clk \text{ or } steel} + q_{indir,clk \text{ or } steel}$$

- Carbonator CO₂ capture efficiency

$$E_{carb} [\%] = \frac{\dot{m}_{CO_2,captured,carbonator}}{\dot{m}_{CO_2,in,carbonator}}$$

Where $\dot{m}_{CO_2,captured,carbonator}$ is the CO₂ mass flow rate captured in the carbonator and $\dot{m}_{CO_2,in,carbonator}$ is the mass flow rate of CO₂ entering the carbonator with the gas.

- Plant electric power penalty due to CCS

$$\Delta P_{el} [MW_e] = P_{el,Plant \text{ with } CCS} - P_{el,plant \text{ without } CCS}$$

Where $P_{el,Plant \text{ with } CCS}$ is the electric power in the plant with CCS system and $P_{el,plant \text{ without } CCS}$ is the is the electric power in the plant without CCS system.

- Direct (Scope 1) CO₂ emissions

$$e_{dir,CO_2} \left[\frac{kg_{CO_2}}{t_{MSW \text{ or } wood \text{ or } clk \text{ or } steel}} \right] = \frac{\dot{m}_{CO_2,at \text{ stack}}}{\dot{m}_{waste \text{ fuel } \text{ or } \dot{m}_{wood} \text{ or } \dot{m}_{clinker} \text{ or } \dot{m}_{steel}}$$

Where $\dot{m}_{CO_2,at \text{ stack}}$ is the CO₂ mass flow rate emitted at the stack of the plant.

- Indirect (Scope 2) CO₂ emissions

$$e_{indir,CO_2} \left[\frac{kg_{CO_2}}{t_{MSW \text{ or wood or clk or steel}}} \right] = \frac{P_{el,Plant \text{ with CCS}} \cdot e_{CO_2,ref_{el}}}{\dot{m}_{waste \text{ fuel OR } \dot{m}_{wood \text{ OR } \dot{m}_{clinker \text{ OR } \dot{m}_{steel}}}}$$

Where:

$e_{CO_2,ref_{el}}$ is the European electrical CO₂ emission factor (265 kg_{CO₂}/MWh_e) (European Environment Agency, 2023).

- Equivalent CO₂ emissions

$$e_{eq,CO_2} \left[\frac{kg_{CO_2}}{t_{MSW \text{ or wood or clk or steel}}} \right] = e_{dir,CO_2} + e_{indir,CO_2}$$

- CO₂ avoided from flue gases

$$CO_2 \text{ avoided } [\%] = 1 - \frac{e_{dir,CO_2 \text{ with CCS}}}{e_{dir,CO_2 \text{ without CCS}}}$$

Where $e_{dir,CO_2 \text{ with CCS}}$ are the direct CO₂ emissions of the plant with CCS system and $e_{dir,CO_2 \text{ without CCS}}$ are the direct CO₂ emissions of the plant without CCS system.

- CO₂ Capture Rate

$$CCR [\%] = 1 - \frac{\dot{m}_{C,to \text{ plant stack}}}{\dot{m}_{C,in}}$$

Where $\dot{m}_{C,in}$ is the carbon entering the plant by means of fuel, air and process streams (e.g. from the raw meal in cement, from limestone and other feedstock in steel, etc.) and $\dot{m}_{C,to \text{ plant stack}}$ is the carbon leaving the plant at the stack.

- SPECCA (Specific Primary Energy Consumption for CO₂ avoided)

$$SPECCA \left[\frac{MJ_{LHV}}{kg_{CO_2}} \right] = \frac{\dot{Q}_{plant \text{ with CCS}} - \dot{Q}_{plant \text{ without CCS}} - \frac{\Delta P_e}{\eta_{el,ref}}}{\dot{m}_{CO_2,plant \text{ without CCS}} - \dot{m}_{CO_2,plant \text{ with CCS}} + \dot{m}_{CO_2,plant \text{ el,ref}}}$$

Where:

- $\dot{Q}_{plant \text{ with CCS}}$ is the total thermal input of the plant with CCS for the cases WtE and Bio-CHP, comprehensive of the thermal input of the plant and that of the calciner. For the cement and steel cases this term corresponds to the specific equivalent energy consumption ($q_{eq,clk \text{ or steel}}$)
- $\dot{Q}_{plant \text{ without CCS}}$ is the thermal input of the reference plant for the WtE and Bio-CHP cases. For cement and steel cases this term corresponds to the specific equivalent energy consumption ($q_{eq,clk \text{ or steel}}$) of the reference cases
- $\frac{\Delta P_e}{\eta_{el,ref}}$ (only for the WtE and Bio-CHP cases) quantifies the thermal input of a plant that uses the same fuel as the calciner to produce electricity (it considers that the additional electricity ΔP_e generated by the CaL was previously generated by the equivalent plant that is not operating in with CCS)

- $\dot{m}_{CO_2,plant\ without\ CCS}$ are the CO₂ emissions of the plant without the CCS for the WtE and Bio-CHP cases. For cement and steel cases this term corresponds to the specific equivalent CO₂ emissions (e_{eq,CO_2}) of the reference cases
- $\dot{m}_{CO_2,plant\ with\ CCS}$ are the CO₂ emissions of the plant with the CCS for the WtE and Bio-CHP cases. For cement and steel cases this term corresponds to the specific equivalent CO₂ emissions (e_{eq,CO_2})
- $\dot{m}_{CO_2,plant\ el,ref}$ (only for the WtE and Bio-CHP cases) quantifies the indirect CO₂ emissions that are avoided from the of the equivalent plant to produce the additional electricity ΔP_e

3.2 Economic KPIs

For the economic analyses, the assumptions listed in Table 14 have been considered.

Table 14: Main assumptions for economic analysis. Note ^{a)}: Inflation-adjusted discount rate is computed accounting for 50% debt capital (with 8% interest), 50% equity capital (with 8% interest), and 3% inflation.

Plant operational life	yrs	25
Depreciation duration	yrs	25
Inflation adjusted discount rate ^{a)}	-	5%
# of additional workers required	-	20
Worker unitary cost	€/y	60 000
Tax rate	-	30%
Insurance and local taxes	%TPC/y	2.5%
Fixed Maintenance cost	%TPC/y	2.0%
Maintenance labour cost	% of maint. costs	40%
Administrative and support cost	% of oper. & maint. costs	30%
CO ₂ transport and storage costs	€/t _{CO2}	15
Electricity selling price (average value in EU27 years 2019-2023 - (Eurostat, 2023a))	€/MWh _e	80.675
Electricity purchase price (average value in EU27 years 2019-2023 - (Eurostat, 2023a))	€/MWh _e	168.2
Coal price (for cement - (CEMCAP, 2018b))	€/GJ _{LHV}	3.0
Natural gas price-average value for non-household EU consumers (average value in EU27 years 2019-2023 - (Eurostat, 2023b))	€/MWh _{LHV}	51.70
Carbon tax	€/t _{CO2}	80

The methodology followed in this report for the economic analysis is in line with the CEMCAP framework (CEMCAP, 2018b) with some updates on the electricity and fuel costs and on the CO₂ tax price. In particular, the Total Plant Cost (TPC), has been then computed adding process contingencies, indirect costs, project contingencies and owner's costs, following the bottom-up approach depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: TPC estimation sequence based on CEMCAP D3.2 deliverable (CEMCAP, 2018b).

The following economic KPIs are considered:

- Cost of CO₂ avoided: defined as the break-even carbon-tax, i.e. the value of the carbon tax at reference year 2023 (assumed constant for the whole plant life) that would allow the Net Present Value of the plant to be zero, considering an operational life of 25 years;
- Incremental cost of the useful product: for the cement and steel cases it is the increase in the production cost of decarbonized cement and steel compared to the current production cost; for the WtE case it is the increase in the gate-fee associated with waste disposal with CCS, compared to the current gate-fee; for the Bio-CHP case it is the increase in the cost for electricity production, compared to the current production costs.

4 INTEGRATION WITH MEA-BASED SOLVENT CO₂ CAPTURE SYSTEM

In this section, simulation results of integration of the four reference plants with a conventional post-combustion MEA-based solvent system for CO₂ capture are presented. For all cases, it was decided to place the MEA system downstream of the reference plant, as an end-of-pipe system, sized for capturing around 90% of the CO₂ contained in the flue gas entering the absorber. Differently from the other cases, the target CO₂ removal efficiency in the absorber was set to 95% for the nominal operating conditions. This design specification should guarantee a safety margin to cope for the unsteady conditions of the steel plant.

The main assumptions used for the MEA system simulations are listed in Table 15. Figure 6 shows the schematic of the system considered in this report.

 Figure 6: Schematic of MEA CO₂ capture system considered in this report.

Table 15: Main assumptions adopted for MEA cases simulations

Minimum temperature difference in gas-gas heat exchanger, °C	~40
Direct Contact Cooler packing height, m	7
Direct Contact Cooler gas outlet temperature, °C	40
Content of MEA in the aqueous solvent solution, %wt.	30%
Absorber packed height, m	20
Absorber packing type, -	MELLAPAK 250Y (structured)
Approach to flood in the absorber, %	~70%
Minimum ΔT in lean-rich heat exchanger, °C	10
Pressure drop in lean-rich heat exchanger, bar	1
Stripper packed height, m	8
Stripper packing type, -	MELLAPAK 250Y (structured)
Approach to flood in the stripper, %	~70%
Top condenser nominal temperature, °C	40
Top condenser nominal pressure, bar	1.9
Reboiler nominal pressure, bar	2.0
Lean solvent loading, -	0.20
Water washing packing height, m	3
Number of stages of intercooled compression, -	4
CO ₂ delivery pressure, bar	110
CO ₂ delivery temperature, °C	40

An important parameter for the MEA system design and performance is the lean loading considered for the solvent regeneration, and defined as the molar ratio between the CO₂ in the solvent and the total amount of MEA. Although optimization is not performed, in this work the assumed lean loading and the columns sizing criteria are in line with other works dealing with optimization of MEA system design (Agbonghae et al., 2014; Danaci et al., 2021; Gjernes et

al., 2017; Michailos and Gibbins, 2022; Rezazadeh et al., 2016; Rochelle et al., 2024). For all the case studies, a total packing height of 20m was fixed in the absorption column, while in the desorption column it was set to 8 m. For a given lean loading and packing height in the absorber, the L/G ratio was selected to achieve the target CO₂ removal rate.

As depicted in Figure 6, the CO₂-containing flue gas taken from the reference plant (#1) is first sent to a regenerative gas-gas heat exchanger, for initial cooling (#2) and then sent to the direct contact cooler (DCC), where the final cooling takes place. The flue gases exit the DCC at ~40°C and are sent to the absorber column (#3), where they are contacted with a 30%_{wt.} MEA solution, which removes about 90% of the incoming CO₂(and 95% for the application in steel making process). The last packing section (3 m) of the absorber column are dedicated to the water wash section to keep MEA and volatile degradation products into the circulating liquid phase. Finally, the CO₂-lean gases (#5) leaving the absorber are sent to the regenerative gas-gas heat exchanger, where they are heated to a temperature of ~80°C, and sent to the stack (#10). In order to overcome the pressure drop in the system, a fan is placed before the DCC section.

The CO₂-enriched solvent exiting the absorption column (#4) is first sent to the lean-rich heat exchanger, where it is preheated to a temperature of ~70°C and then sent to the stripper for regeneration (#6). The stripper is an 8 m high column where the top condenser operates at 40°C and 1.9 bar, while the reboiler has an operating temperature of about 120-125°C and an operating pressure of 2 bar. The regenerated solvent (#8) is then sent first to the regenerative lean-rich heat exchanger and then to a final cooler and to the absorber (#9).

The pure CO₂ stream leaving the stripper top condenser (#7) is cooled and compressed to a final pressure of 110 bar in a 4-stages intercooled compression section and sent to transport and storage (#11) via pipeline.

For each specific application (cement, WtE, Bio-CHP or steel), the L/G (i.e. the flow rate of lean solvent) is adjusted to reach the target capture rate.

4.1 Heat & Material balances, integrated system and technical KPIs

4.1.1 Cement application

Figure 7 shows the schematic of MEA system integrated in the reference cement plant described in section 2.1. The MEA CO₂ capture system is placed after the mill section of the cement plant and before the stack. The flue gas flow rate and composition after the mill is reported in Table 16.

Table 16: Flue gas flow rate and composition from mill cement plant (stream exiting the raw meal fan).

Flue gas from cement plant	Nm ³ /h (1.013 bar, 0°C)	264'992
Temperature	°C	120
Ar	%vol, wet basis	0.68
N ₂	%vol, wet basis	57.29
O ₂	%vol, wet basis	7.69
CO ₂	%vol, wet basis	19.56
H ₂ O	%vol, wet basis	14.78

Figure 7: Schematic of integration of MEA CO₂ capture system in the reference cement plant (dashed red lines represent the thermal integration for solvent regeneration).

The heat required by the MEA system reboiler, for solvent regeneration, is partially provided by heat recovery from the clinker cooler vent gas (which are cooled down from 300°C to 135°C, generating saturated steam at 130°C), which supplies about 5% of the required thermal power. The remaining heat is provided by a natural gas boiler, with a thermal efficiency of 92%_{LHV}. In order to keep a high total CO₂ capture efficiency, the CO₂ from natural gas combustion was also captured by sending the natural boiler off-gases in the absorber along with the flue gases from the cement plant. The CO₂ from natural gas combustion corresponds to about 21% of the CO₂ generated in the overall system (due to the large amount of thermal energy requested for solvent regeneration). The flow rate and composition of the flue gases entering the DCC of MEA system is reported in Table 17.

Table 17: Flue gas flow rate and composition entering the DCC of MEA CO₂ capture system.

Flue gas entering MEA system	Nm ³ /h (1.013 bar, 0°C)	441'626
Temperature	°C	60
Ar	%vol, wet basis	0.75
N ₂	%vol, wet basis	62.85
O ₂	%vol, wet basis	5.80
CO ₂	%vol, wet basis	15.07
H ₂ O	%vol, wet basis	15.53

In Table 18, the heat and mass balances, and the energy based KPIs of the system are reported.

 Table 18: Heat & mass balances and energy based KPIs for reference cement plant integrated with MEA CO₂ capture system.

		Reference cement plant	Cement plant with MEA CO ₂ capture system
Clinker production	tpd	2824	2824
Total direct fuel consumption ($q_{dir,clk}$)	MW _{LHV} -MJ _{LHV} /kg _{clk}	105.9 - 3.24	241.5 - 7.38
<i>Coal consumption (clinker burning line)</i>	<i>MW_{LHV}-MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk}</i>	<i>105.9 - 3.24</i>	<i>105.9 - 3.24</i>
<i>Natural gas consumption (solvent regeneration)</i>	<i>MW_{LHV}-MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk}</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>135.3 - 4.14</i>
Electricity consumption for cement making	MW _e -kWh _e /t _{clk}	4.30 - 131.6	4.30 - 131.6
Additional electricity consumption for CO ₂ capture	MW _e -kWh _e /t _{clk}	-	18.87 - 160.3
<i>Fans</i>	<i>MW_e-kWh_e/t_{clk}</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>3.01 - 25.5</i>
<i>CO₂ compression</i>	<i>MW_e-kWh_e/t_{clk}</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>11.05 - 93.9</i>
<i>Auxiliaries (MEA pumps, extra cooling water, etc.)</i>	<i>MW_e-kWh_e/t_{clk}</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>4.81 - 40.9</i>
Total electricity consumption	MW _e -kWh _e /t _{clk}	4.30 - 131.6	23.17 - 291.9
CO₂ emissions and KPIs			
CO ₂ captured in absorber	%	-	90.7
CO ₂ avoided from flue gases (cement kiln only)	%	-	88.2
CO ₂ captured	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	-	24.9 - 762.8
Direct CO ₂ emissions at stack ($e_{dir,CO2}$)	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	28.3 - 864.7	3.33 - 101.9
Indirect CO ₂ emission ($e_{indir,CO2}$)	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	1.14 - 34.9	2.5 - 77.4
Equivalent CO ₂ emission ($e_{eq,CO2}$)	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	29.4 - 899.6	5.9 - 179.3
Equivalent CO ₂ avoidance rate	%	-	79.7
Equivalent primary energy consumption	MW _{LHV} -MJ _{LHV} /kg _{clk}	114.3 - 3.50	286.8 - 8.76
Equivalent primary energy consumption increase	%	-	150.5
SPECCA	MJ _{LHV} /kg _{CO2}	-	7.31

With this system it is possible to achieve a CO₂ avoidance from flue gases of about 88%. The specific reboiler duty per ton of CO₂ captured is around 4.0 MJ_{th}/kg_{CO2}. The primary energy consumption of the system is about 7.38 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk}, corresponding to an increase of about 128% respect to the reference cement plant (3.24 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk}). The system electricity consumption increases of about 122% (291.9 vs 131.6 kWh_e/t_{clk}) and is mainly due to the compression of captured CO₂, which consumes about 11.1 MW_e. Indirect CO₂ emissions associated to electricity consumption are ~77.5 kg_{CO2}/t_{clk}. Therefore, the equivalent CO₂ emissions and the equivalent primary energy consumption are 179.3 kg_{CO2}/t_{clk} and 8.76 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk} respectively. The equivalent CO₂ avoidance rate is therefore about 80%, lower than the reduction in direct CO₂ emissions (~88%), due to the increase in the electrical consumption

of the whole system and thus the consequent increase in indirect CO₂ emissions (Scope 2) of the overall plant (77.5 vs 34.9 kg_{CO2}/t_{clk}). Finally, the SPECCA of the system thus turns out to be 7.31 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO2}.

4.1.2 Waste to Energy and Bio-CHP applications

Also for the WtE and Bio-CHP sectors, the MEA CO₂ capture plant is located downstream of the host plant, after the flue gas treatment section and before the stack, as shown in Figure 8. However, in these cases, unlike the cement sector application, the heat required for solvent regeneration in the reboiler is provided by a 2.7 bar (saturated temperature of ~130°C) bleed from the main steam turbine in the plant. Table 7 and Table 9 report the flow rates and compositions of the flue gases entering the MEA CO₂ capture system for WtE and Bio-CHP cases, respectively.

Figure 8: Schematic of the integration of MEA CO₂ capture system in WtE and Bio-CHP plants.

In Table 19, the heat and mass balances and the technical KPIs of the two plants are reported.

Table 19: Heat & mass balances and technical KPIs for reference WtE and Bio-CHP plants integrated with MEA CO₂ capture system.

		WtE plant		Bio-CHP plant	
		Reference	MEA CO ₂ capture system	Reference	MEA CO ₂ capture system
Fuel consumption	MW _{LHV} - tph	243.1 – 87.5	243.1 - 87.5	135.3 – 26.3	135.3 – 26.3
Gross steam turbine power output	MW _e - kWh _e /t _{MSW} or wood	77.0 – 880.0	60.7 - 693.1	43.4 – 1652.1	36.3 - 1381.1
Plant auxiliaries electrical power consumption	MW _e - kWh _e /t _{MSW} or wood	7.0 – 80.0	22.1 - 252.3	4.3 – 153.8	9.7 - 368.3
<i>Steam cycle auxiliaries and BOP</i>	<i>MW_e - kWh_e/t_{MSW} or wood</i>	<i>7.0 – 80.0</i>	<i>7.0 - 80.0</i>	<i>4.3 – 153.8</i>	<i>4.3 - 163.5</i>
<i>Fans</i>	<i>MW_e - kWh_e/t_{MSW} or wood</i>	-	<i>3.0 - 34.1</i>	-	<i>0.9 - 33.3</i>
<i>CO₂ compression</i>	<i>MW_e - kWh_e/t_{MSW} or wood</i>	-	<i>7.9 - 89.9</i>	-	<i>2.5 - 95.9</i>
<i>Auxiliaries (MEA pumps, extra cooling water, etc.)</i>	<i>MW_e - kWh_e/t_{MSW} or wood</i>	-	<i>4.2 - 48.4</i>	-	<i>2.0 - 75.7</i>
Net electrical power output	MW _e - kWh _e /t _{MSW} or wood	70.0 - 800	38.6 - 440.8	39.1 – 1498.3	26.6 - 1012.8
CO ₂ emissions and KPIs					
Gross electric efficiency	%	31.68	24.95	32.08	26.85
Plant net electric power penalty due to CCS	MW _e - kWh _e /t _{MSW} or wood	-	31.4 - 359.2	-	12.5 - 473.9
Net electric efficiency	% _{LHV}	28.80	15.87	28.90	19.69
Net electric efficiency penalty	%pts.	-	12.93	-	9.21
CO ₂ captured in absorber	%	-	90.2	-	90.1
Direct CO ₂ emissions at stack (e _{dir,CO2})	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{MSW} or wood	23.2 – 952.4	2.3 - 93.6	9.8 – 1342.0	1.0 - 132.8
CO ₂ avoided from flue gases	%	-	90.2	-	90.1
Total CO ₂ captured	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{MSW} or wood	-	20.9 - 858.8	-	8.9 - 1212.7
Net direct fossil emissions ¹⁾	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{MSW} or wood	11.6 – 476.2	-11.6 - -531.5	0.0 – 0.0	-7.9 - -1079.9
Indirect CO ₂ emission (e _{indir,CO2})	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{MSW} or wood	-	2.3 - 93.2	-	0.9 - 125.6
Equivalent CO ₂ emission (e _{eq,CO2})	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{MSW} or wood	11.6 – 476.2	4.6 - 188.8	0.0 – 0.0	1.9 - 258.4
Equivalent CO ₂ avoidance rate	%	-	80.2	-	80.8
SPECCA	MJ _{LHV} /kg _{CO2}	-	3.30	-	3.06

¹⁾ net emissions account for the biogenic share of the carbon in the fuel and for indirect emissions. Biogenic CO₂ is considered to be climate neutral. Both plants reach carbon-negativity (i.e. they remove carbon from the atmosphere)

About 79.9 MW_{th} are required for solvent regeneration in the WtE case, corresponding in a specific reboiler duty per ton of CO₂ captured of about 3.8 MJ_{th}/kg_{CO2}. This thermal power is provided by steam turbine bleeding at about 2.7 bar, which corresponds to a reduction in gross electrical power output from the steam turbine of about 16.4 MW_e. Similarly, for the Bio-CHP plant, about 35.8 MW_{th} are required at the reboiler (corresponding to a specific reboiler duty per ton of CO₂ captured of about 4.0 MJ_{th}/kg_{CO2}), which corresponds to a gross electric power loss in the steam

turbine of about 7.1 MW_e. In both cases, the loss of electrical output due to bleeding for solvent regeneration represents largest energy penalty of the plant, followed by the electricity required for the CO₂ compression. Considering the additional electrical consumption of the overall plant, the net electrical efficiency of both plants drops from ~29% (see Table 10) to about 15.9% for WtE case and to about 19.7% for Bio-CHP case, corresponding to a net electric efficiency penalty of about 12.9 and 9.2%pts, respectively for WtE and Bio-CHP cases. The reduction in net power output is associated with indirect CO₂ emissions of 93.2 kg_{CO2}/t_{MSW} and 125.6 kg_{CO2}/t_{wood}, respectively for the WtE and Bio-CHP cases. This results in equivalent CO₂ emissions of the plants being 188.8 kg_{CO2}/t_{MSW} for the WtE case and 258.4 kg_{CO2}/t_{wood} for the Bio-CHP case, corresponding to an equivalent CO₂ avoidance rate of the overall plant of 80.2% and 80.8% for WtE and Bio-CHP cases respectively. Finally, the SPECCA index values result to be 3.30 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO2} and 3.06 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO2} for the WtE and Bio-CHP plants, respectively.

4.1.3 Steel application

The fluctuations of flow rate and composition of the flue gases during the cycle of the reference EAF plant require a more detailed analysis of the heat and mass balances and sizing of the post-combustion capture plant. Differently from the previous case studies, the MEA-based capture system for the steel case has to be evaluated in different operating conditions to cope with the variations in the EAF flue gases. Specifically, six quasi-steady-state operating points (A, B, C, D, E, F) have been identified as representative of the whole cyclic behaviour (no dynamic behaviour is considered in this work and it is assumed that for the mass and energy balance analysis, the operation can be simulated as a sequence of different steady-state conditions). Section 2.3 presents the detailed logic behind those representative cases, including for each of them the flue gases specifications (Volume flow rate, temperature and gas composition). Case A represents the largest load scenario for the MEA system (maximum flow rate and highest CO₂ molar concentration), and therefore, the capture plant is designed and sized for these conditions (design point). Once the on-design operations (case A) and the corresponding plant sizing are defined, the off-design process simulation of the MEA capture plant can be evaluated (case B, C, D, E, F) assuming a fixed geometry for the absorber and stripper. Figure 9 shows the schematic of integration of MEA CO₂ capture plant in the EAF steel making plant.

Figure 9: Schematic of integration of MEA CO₂ capture system in the reference EAF steel making plant (dashed red lines represent the thermal integration for solvent regeneration).

As done in the cement case study, also for the EAF process it is assumed that a natural gas-fired boiler is installed to provide the required thermal duty in the reboiler, due to the lack of waste heat in the process. As a consequence of the relatively high temperature of the flue gases flowing to the MEA system, a waste heat recovery steam generator is considered to be installed upstream the DCC to cool down the flue gases to 160°C and produce steam at 140°C for the reboiler. The sizing and CAPEX estimation for this heat exchanger unit have been retrieved from Thermoflex. The installation of the waste heat recovery steam generator enables to reduce the required nominal thermal duty of the natural gas boiler. This unit operation is sized to provide a constant useful thermal power of 8.9 MW_{th} (40.4% of the nominal thermal power requirement). This value guarantees that the reboiler duty is fully covered in all the operating points of the EAF cycle, taking into account also the thermal power recovered from EAF flue gases. The boiler is sized on the average duty and coupled with a thermal storage system, while the heat required for regeneration varies according to the specific operating point. It is therefore assumed that, when the net reboiler duty is below the nominal power of the boiler, there is an accumulation of the steam produced that is exploited when the reboiler duty exceeds the natural gas boiler rated power.

Another peculiarity of this case study is represented by the off-design operations of the packed columns in the MEA absorption plant. In fact, the column dimensioning has been carried out for the on-design flow rates, but the plant is operated for most of the cycle in different conditions. Under off-design conditions, the flue gas flow rate at the absorber inlet is lower compared to the design point, and the liquid solvent flow rate is reduced accordingly, down to a minimum value (minimum turndown) which prevents from reaching critical conditions for the column hydraulics (Green and Perry, 2008; Oh et al., 2024; SULZER, 2022). The column turndown ratio or, in other words, the minimum liquid and gas flow rates in which the column can be operated, were assumed to be 15% of the nominal conditions. When the gas flow rate is not sufficient for guaranteeing such operations, the minimum value is achieved by mixing ambient air in addition to flue gases entering the column (cases E and F).

The results from the Aspen Plus process simulations for the EAF plant equipped with MEA-based CO₂ capture are reported in Table 20.

Table 20: Aspen Plus process simulation results for the MEA- based post combustion CO₂ capture applied in the reference steel plant. These results include plant design and sizing based on on-design conditions (case A), and the heat & mass balances for all the operating points of the EAF cycle.

		Average cycle values	A (DESIGN)	B	C	D	E	F
DCC diameter	m	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Lean solvent flow rate	kg/s	80.77	216.47	133.88	69.55	28.51	32.95	32.95
Flue gas flow rate – Absorber inlet	kg/s	55.15	112.97	88.16	60.48	31.65	16.87	17.19
Flue gas flow rate – Absorber inlet	Nm ³ /h	154'467	315'212	246'310	169'697	89'161	47'473	48'460
CO ₂ concentration – Absorber inlet	%vol	3.67%	6.04%	4.78%	3.59%	2.75%	2.99%	2.07%
L/G mass	kg/kg	1.483	1.916	1.519	1.150	0.901	1.954	1.917
Absorber diameter	m	7.50	7.50	7.50	7.50	7.50	7.50	7.5
CO ₂ rich loading	mol _{CO2} /mol _{MEA}	0.388	0.420	0.424	0.425	0.422	0.312	0.279
CO ₂ capture rate	%	97.6%	95.1%	96.5%	97.5%	98.2%	98.9%	98.9%
Gas flow rate to CO ₂ compressor	Nm ³ /h	6'660	18'824	11'829	6'184	2'499	1'459	1'036
CO ₂ mass flow rate (captured)	kg/h	12'556	35'493	22'304	11'660	4'710	2'749	1'948
Stripper column diameter	m	3.50	3.50	3.50	3.50	3.50	3.50	3.50
Specific reboiler duty	MJ/kg _{CO2}	4.78	4.20	4.16	4.13	4.15	5.87	7.03
Heat recovery for steam production (160°C)	kW	5'915	19'377	11'561	5'317	1'229	207	0
Reboiler duty	kW _{th}	14'903	41'386	25'753	13'376	5'429	4'484	3'804
Net thermal power consumption provided by the boiler	kW _{th}	8'989	22'009	14'192	8'059	4'200	4'277	3'804

4.2 Economic analysis

4.2.1 Cement application

This section reports the outcomes of the economic analysis for the reference cement plant equipped with MEA-based CO₂ capture. The Total Plant Cost (TPC) of the capture unit is equal to 237.8 M€, and the breakdown of the installed equipment cost (149.9 M€) is depicted in Figure 10. The largest share of the MEA system Capex is due to the CO₂ compression section (30% of the total installed cost) and the absorber, stripper and DCC columns (around 37% of the total installed cost).

Figure 10: Breakdown of the Total Installed Cost for the MEA-based capture system applied to the reference cement plant.

The results of the economic analysis in terms of Cost of CO₂ avoided (CCA) and the increase cost of clinker are reported in Table 21 and Figure 11. The price of natural gas is assumed equal to 51.7 €/MWh.

The CCA for this application is equal to 185€/t_{CO2}, of which, of which 84€/t_{CO2} (46%) are attributable to the fuel consumption for the reboiler.

For a carbon tax of 80 €/t_{CO2}, the cost of clinker due to MEA-based CCS increases by 79.84 €/t_{clk}, and the fuel consumption for solvent regeneration is the most impactful item.

Table 21: Breakdown of the Cost of CO₂ Avoided (CCA) and the breakeven cost of clinker increase for the reference cement plant equipped with MEA-based CO₂ capture.

		Cost of CO₂ avoided €/t_{CO2}
Natural gas for steam supply	€/t _{CO2}	84.22
Electricity	€/t _{CO2}	35.36
Other OPEX (incl. CO ₂ transport and storage)	€/t _{CO2}	41.18
Total OPEX	€/t_{CO2}	160.76
CAPEX	€/t_{CO2}	23.91
Cost of CO₂ avoided	€/t_{CO2}	184.67
		Clinker cost increase €/t_{clk}
Natural gas for steam supply	€/t _{clk}	64.24
Electricity	€/t _{clk}	26.97
Carbon tax	€/t _{clk}	-61.02
Other OPEX (incl. CO ₂ transport and storage)	€/t _{clk}	31.41
Total OPEX	€/t_{clk}	61.60
CAPEX	€/t_{clk}	18.24
Incremental cost of clinker due to CCS €/t_{clk}	€/t_{clk}	79.84

Figure 11: Breakdown of the Cost of CO₂ Avoided (CCA) and the breakeven cost of clinker increase for the cement plant case with MEA system.

4.2.2 Waste to Energy and Bio-CHP applications

The Total Installed Cost of the MEA capture unit applied to the **WtE plant** is 114.0 M€ and its breakdown is reported in Figure 12. The Total Plant Cost is equal to 180.8 M€.

The CCA of the WtE case is estimated in ~95€/t_{CO2} and the breakeven gate-fee increment is equal to ~12 €/t_{MSW}. As the WtE plant with CCS results to be a net negative emission process, in this scenario carbon credits are recognized to the WtE operator (and assumed to be valorized on the market at the CO₂ tax price of 80 €/t_{CO2}) for capturing the biogenic fraction of CO₂ (BECCS approach); as a result, a revenue of 45 €/t_{MSW} is introduced for the WtE operator and this partly compensate the extra cost for CCS. In this scenario, the overall yearly amount of CO₂ captured is considered for the carbon credits in the economic analysis, with no distinctions between biogenic and fossil fraction. In WtE application there is no need for the installation of a dedicated boiler for steam generation, but steam is bled from the turbine of the power cycle. The results of this analysis are reported in Figure 13. In this case, the loss of electricity production caused by the bleeding from the steam turbine represents the most significant contribution of the CCA value and the breakeven gate-fee price (considering an electricity selling price of 80.675 €/MWh).

Figure 12: Breakdown of the Total Installed Cost for the MEA-based capture system applied to the reference WtE plant.

Figure 13: Breakdown of the Cost of CO₂ Avoided (CCA) and the breakeven gate-fee increment for the WtE plant case with MEA system.

For the **Bio-CHP plant**, the Total Plant Cost of the MEA CO₂ capture unit is 104.52 M€ and the Total Installed Cost is estimated in 65.89 M€. The breakdown of the Total Installed Cost is reported in Figure 14.

Similarly to the WtE plant, even in this case study the reboiler duty for solvent regeneration is covered via steam bleeding from the steam turbine. Consequently, the electricity production of the Bio-CHP plant is decreased by 9.21%pt.

The results of the economic analysis for the Bio-CHP case are displayed in Figure 15 in terms of cost of CO₂ avoided (110.92 €/t_{CO2}) and increment of the breakeven electricity price (37.03 €/MWh). In this case, CAPEX and loss of

electricity production are the items with the highest impact. The first one accounts for 26%, while the latter corresponds with almost the 28% of the CCA.

Figure 14: Breakdown of the Total Installed Cost for the MEA-based capture system applied to the reference Bio-CHP plant.

Figure 15: Breakdown of the Cost of CO₂ Avoided (CCA) and the breakeven electricity price increase for the Bio-CHP case with MEA system.

4.2.3 Steel application

A Total Plant Cost of 136.52 M€ and a total installed equipment cost of 86.06 M€ (Figure 16) was obtained for the Electric Arc furnace with MEA CO₂ capture plant. In this case the CAPEX share due to the columns is nearly half of the total cost, a contribution increased compared to other scenarios (e.g. cement) due to the lower plant capacity and more diluted CO₂ concentration in flue gases. The results of the economic analysis for the steel reference case are displayed in Figure 17 in terms of cost of CO₂ avoided (345 €/t_{CO2}) and increment of the cost of steel (25 €/t). The high value of CCA reflects the fact that the CO₂ capture system is sized for the nominal capacity (peak conditions), but the capacity factor of the EAF plant is relatively low and the CO₂ capture plant operates for most of the time below the nominal capacity. Indeed, the fraction of CAPEX accounts for almost 33% of the overall CCA value, a significant portion especially if compared to other similar sectors (e.g. cement where the CAPEX contributed for 13% of the CCA value).

On the other hand, the increment in the specific cost of steel is relatively low, accounting for few percentage points of the actual price of steel produced via the EAF without carbon capture. This is because EAF steelmaking has already a limited CO₂ emission footprint (i.e. around 0.07 t_{CO2}/t_{steel}) compared to other steelmaking routes. This is the reason why, although significant relative reduction in CO₂ emissions (around 95% of CO₂ avoidance) due to CCS provides a high CCA, the impact on the cost of steel is rather limited.

Figure 16: Breakdown of the Total Installed Cost for the MEA-based capture system applied to the reference steel plant.

Figure 17: Breakdown of the Cost of CO₂ Avoided (CCA) and the breakeven electricity price increase for the Electric Arc Furnace case with MEA system.

5 INTEGRATION WITH CALCIUM LOOPING CO₂ CAPTURE SYSTEM

This section describes the integration of benchmark fluidized bed CaL systems in the different reference plants described in Section 2.

5.1 Auxiliary process units

Independently of the sector considered, the Calcium Looping CO₂ capture technology needs auxiliary unit operations, namely: an air separation unit (ASU) and a CO₂ purification unit (CPU).

5.1.1 Air Separation Unit (ASU)

Oxy-combustion in the calciner of CaL systems provides the energy necessary to sustain the endothermic calcination reaction. Given the high oxygen demand, a cryogenic air separation unit (ASU) has been considered, delivering oxygen with 95%mol purity which results in an electricity consumption in the range of 240-250 kWh_e/t_{O₂}. The cost of the ASU was estimated from the internal routines of THERMOFLEX v31.

5.1.2 CO₂ compression and purification unit (CPU)

The CO₂-rich stream leaving the CaL plant has to meet purity specifications for CO₂ purity, concentration of other species (such as O₂), pressure and temperature. The model of the CPU considered in this thesis was developed by Magli et al. (Magli et al., 2021) to deliver a stream with CO₂ content >99.5%_{vol}, O₂ < 10 ppm_v, H₂O < 1 ppm_v. In Figure 18 the flowsheet of CPU is reported. The impure CO₂-stream is compressed in an intercooled compression train, gets dehydrated by water sorption and cooled down to a temperature close to -50°C, exploiting auto-refrigeration process. The cryogenic CO₂ purification box includes a multi-stream low-temperature heat exchanger with a flash tank, in order to minimize the CO₂ lost from the vent gas. The obtained liquid stream, containing the majority of the CO₂ present in the feed gas, is sent to a stripping column. The obtained high-purity CO₂ is evaporated in the multi-stream heat exchanger and sent to the final inter-cooled compressor train for compression to 110 bar. The incondensable gases leaving the flash tank contribute to the impure CO₂ cooling and are vented to the atmosphere.

Figure 18 Schematic of CO₂ compression and purification unit considered in this report (Magli et al., 2019).

For an in-depth discussion of the model used, the reader is referred to (Magli et al., 2021, 2019).

5.2 Heat & Material balances, integrated system and technical KPIs

5.2.1 Cement application

The integration of the CaL system in the reference cement plant is based in the use of interconnected CFB reactors as the core elements for CO₂ capture (carbonator) and calcination of raw meal (calcliner) for subsequent burning in the rotary kiln. Two integrated CFB CaL configurations have been assessed: (i) a system where coarse limestone particles (solid yellow lines in Figure 19) and fine correctives (dotted yellow lines in Figure 19) are fed to the system and (ii) a system where coarse raw meal (black lines in Figure 19) is fed to the process. The first configuration represents an extreme situation where all the inlet calcium is fed to the plant as limestone. Instead, in cement plants, calcium is often introduced partly or totally as marl and the proposed process should be adapted on the composition of the raw materials fed to each specific plant. The expected performance of plants fed with realistic mixtures will be in between those obtained for the two extreme conditions assessed.

Figure 19: Block scheme of Integrated CFB CaL configurations considered in this work. Two different operational situations have been considered: the yellow lines show the streams of solid material in the case where the limestone (solid lines) is fed separately and with a larger particle size than the correctives (dotted lines) in the raw meal, while the black lines show the case where it is not possible to feed the limestone separately from the other correctives in the raw meal

Figure 13 shows the schematic of the cement plant with integrated CFB CaL process.

Figure 20: Schematic of the cement plant with integrated CFB CaL process.

As described in (De Lena et al., 2022), an important parameter is the limestone CaL split ratio (CaLSR) defined as the percentage of fresh Ca entering the loop of CaL process with respect to the total Ca fed to the plant as pure limestone. Therefore, the CaLSR represents how much CO₂-sorbent material does not fragment becoming fines and remains in

the CaL system. Two cases were analyzed in this deliverable: the first involving the use of pure limestone in the CaL system, and the second involving the use of raw meal as CO₂-sorbent material. In both cases, a CaLSR of 50% was considered. In Table 22 are reported the heat and mass balances, and the energy based KPIs of the whole system, for the both described above.

Table 22: Heat & mass balances and energy based KPIs for reference cement plant integrated with CaL-CFB capture system.

		Cement plant with CFB-CaL Limestone 50%-CaLSR	Cement plant with CFB-CaL Raw Meal 50%-CaLSR
Clinker production	tpd	2824	2820
Total direct fuel consumption ($q_{dir,clk}$)	$MW_{LHV}-MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk}$	161.2 - 4.93	191.8 - 5.88
<i>Fuel consumption in rotary kiln</i>	$MW_{LHV}-MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk}$	40.1 - 1.23	41.1 - 1.26
<i>Fuel consumption in CaL calciner</i>	$MW_{LHV}-MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk}$	121.1 - 3.70	150.7 - 6.62
Oxygen input	tpd-kg _{O2} /kg _{clk}	884.6 - 0.31	1097.8 - 0.39
Electricity consumption cement making	MW_e-kWh_e/t_{clk}	12.04 - 102.3	8.80 - 75.0
Additional electricity consumption for CO ₂ capture	MW_e-kWh_e/t_{clk}	10.02 - 85.2	11.02 - 93.9
<i>Net electricity production in steam cycle</i>	MW_e-kWh_e/t_{clk}	18.46 - 156.9	22.63 - 192.7
<i>ASU consumption</i>	MW_e-kWh_e/t_{clk}	9.19 - 78.1	11.40 - 97.1
<i>Fans consumption in CaL system</i>	MW_e-kWh_e/t_{clk}	1.43 - 12.1	1.71 - 14.6
<i>CO₂ compression consumption</i>	MW_e-kWh_e/t_{clk}	13.74 - 116.8	16.51 - 140.6
<i>Auxiliaries (grinding processes, cooling system, etc.)</i>	MW_e-kWh_e/t_{clk}	4.13 - 35.1	4.02 - 34.26
Total electricity consumption	MW_e-kWh_e/t_{clk}	22.06 - 187.5	19.82 - 168.8
CO₂ emissions and KPIs			
CO ₂ captured in carbonator	%	90.0	90.0
CO ₂ avoided from flue gases	%	93.6	92.6
Overall CO ₂ capture ratio	%	94.7	94.9
Total direct CO ₂ emissions at stack (e_{dir,CO_2})	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	1.8 - 55.2	2.1 - 64.4
<i>Direct CO₂ emissions from kiln flue gases</i>	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	0.5 - 14.6	0.5 - 15.1
<i>Direct CO₂ emissions from CPU vent gas</i>	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	1.3 - 40.6	1.6 - 49.3
Indirect CO ₂ emission (e_{indir,CO_2})	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	1.6 - 49.7	1.5 - 44.7
Equivalent CO ₂ emission (e_{eq,CO_2})	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	3.4 - 104.9	3.6 - 109.2
Equivalent CO ₂ avoidance rate	%	88.3	87.9
Indirect primary energy consumption	$MW_{LHV}-MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk}$	43.0 - 1.3	38.6 - 1.2
Equivalent primary energy consumption	$MW_{LHV}-MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk}$	204.2 - 6.3	230.4 - 7.1
Equivalent primary energy consumption increase	%	50.0	69.6
SPECCA	MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO_2}	2.62	3.67

Due to the reduction in inert solid material recirculation between the calciner and the carbonator of CaL system, the case where limestone is used as CO₂-sorbent results in a lower direct primary energy consumption (~4.93 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk}) than the case where raw meal is used as CO₂-sorbent (~5.88 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk}). As a result, there is also a reduction of about 25% in the oxygen consumption of the system. Electricity consumption also increases in both cases. It can be observed that the higher fuel consumption in the system using raw meal as CO₂-sorbent allows more electricity to be produced from heat recovery. Therefore, the electricity consumption is, for the case with raw meal, about 171.9 kWh_e/t_{clk}

(+30.6% compared to for the reference cement plant), while, for the case with limestone, it is about 189.8 kWh_e/t_{clK} (+44.2% compared to for the reference cement plant). Both cases result in a CO₂ avoided from flue gases of about 92% with a CO₂ capture efficiency in the carbonator of 90%. The overall CO₂ capture efficiency is about 94% in both cases. Considering also the indirect emissions from increased electricity consumption, equivalent CO₂ avoidance rate of about 87% have been obtained in both cases. Due to higher direct primary energy consumption, the case with raw meal as CO₂-sorbent shows a higher increase in equivalent primary energy consumption (+70.1%) than the case with limestone as CO₂-sorbent (+50.4%). Thus it results that the SPECCA index is lower in the case with limestone (~2.7 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO2}) by about 40%, compared with the case using the raw meal as CO₂-sorbent (~3.7 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO2}).

5.2.2 Waste to Energy and Bio-CHP applications

In the **WtE plant**, the CaL carbonator is placed before the wet scrubber, where flue gases are at 120°C (properties resumed in Table 23). Since it is expected that the SO₂ co-capture by the CaL sorbent will exceed the target capture level to comply with the environmental regulations that impose the use of the wet scrubber, it is supposed to remove it, routing the flue gases to the stack at 120°C.

Table 23: WtE flue gases at the inlet of the wet scrubber (comprising both combustion lines)

Flow rate	Nm ³ /h (0°C, 1 atm)	452'510
Mass flow rate	kg/s	155.25
T	°C	120.0
N ₂	%vol, wet basis	65.81
O ₂	%vol, wet basis	6.67%
CO ₂	%vol, wet basis	9.52%
H ₂ O	%vol, wet basis	18.0%
HCl	ppm	10.6
SO ₂	ppm	7.9

The CaL plant is composed of a CFB carbonator reactor, its cyclone and heat recovery section, bag filter and stack, a CFB calciner reactor, its cyclone and heat recovery section and bag filter. The recovered heat is exploited for oxygen preheating and for superheated steam generation. A schematic of the CaL plant is represented in Figure 21. Given the application to a WtE plant, Residue Derived Fuel (RDF), is chosen as the fuel for the calciner. RDF is assumed to be sourced on the market with properties resumed in Table 24. The biogenic carbon content of the RDF is assumed to be the 40% of the total carbon content. The main plant assumptions are reported in Table 25.

Air infiltrations of 1% mass basis in the boiler and 3% in the bag filters have been assumed, given that the plant is operated at negative pressure.

Table 24: attributes of the RDF to be used in the calciner

C	%wt – as received	43.79%
H	%wt – as received	5.87%
N	%wt – as received	0.33%
O	%wt – as received	31.57%
S	%wt – as received	0.06%
Cl	%wt – as received	0.15%
Ash	%wt – as received	3.83%
Moisture	%wt – as received	14.41%
LHV	kJ/kg	16'600

Table 25: details of the CaL plant for WtE application

Superheated steam temperature	°C	500
Superheated steam pressure	bar	60
Condensing type	-	Cooling towers
Condensation pressure	bar	0.086
F_0/F_{CO_2}	-	0.10
F_R/F_{CO_2}	-	8
Carbonator temperature	°C	650
Carbonator CO ₂ capture efficiency	%	89.62%
Carbonator SO ₂ capture efficiency	%	90%
Stack temperature	°C	120
Calciner temperature	°C	920
Oxygen purity	%	95%
Oxygen preheating temperature	°C	140
Oxygen concentration in oxidant gas	%	40%
Oxygen excess at calciner outlet	%vol, wet basis	3.50%
Temperature of the CO ₂ recirculation	°C	400
Cyclone efficiency on Ca particles	%	99.5%
Cyclone efficiency on ash particles	%	90%
Air infiltrations in the Reactors Heat Recovery Sections	%wt.	1%
Air infiltration in bag filters	%wt.	3%

Figure 21: Process flow diagram of the CaL process for the WtE plant.

The CaL make-up ratio F_0/F_{CO_2} and recirculation ratio F_R/F_{CO_2} have been selected to achieve a CO₂ capture efficiency in the carbonator close to 90% while minimizing fuel and oxygen consumption.

The main outcomes from the mass and energy balances are reported in Table 26.

Table 26: Main results of the mass and energy balance of the CaL-WtE plant

RDF (calciner fuel) mass flow	t/h	49.02
RDF power input	kW _{LHV}	230'104
Oxygen mass flow	t/h	74.64
Make-up mass flow	t/h	18.96
CO ₂ to storage	t/h	145.10
Electric power balance		
Steam turbine power	kW_e	76'552
Flue gas FD fan consumption	kW _e	2'864
Flue gas ID fan	kW _e	891
CO ₂ recirculation fan	kW _e	1'322
Condensate pump	kW _e	23
BFW pump	kW _e	642
Cooling Tower loop pump	kW _e	403
Cooling Tower fans	kW _e	524
ASU consumption	kW _e	17'659
CPU consumption	kW _e	24'275
Net electric power output	kW_e	27'948
CO₂ balance		
CO ₂ from WtE	t/h	83.33
CO ₂ from RDF	t/h	78.19
CO ₂ from limestone calcination	t/h	8.33
Total CO₂ IN	t/h	169.85
CO ₂ to storage	t/h	145.00
CO ₂ to stack	t/h	8.65
CO ₂ in CPU vent gases	t/h	15.83
CO ₂ eq. in bag filter solids	t/h	0.37
Total CO₂ OUT	t/h	169.85

In the **Bio CHP plant**, the carbonator is fed with the gas before the stack. The same high-grade wood pellet used in the Bio CHP boiler (properties in Table 8) are used as the calciner fuel. Being the CO₂ concentration in the flue gases higher than that of the WtE application, lower values of F_0/F_{CO_2} and F_R/F_{CO_2} are needed to guarantee CO₂ capture efficiency close to 90%, that provides lower operational costs related to lower fuel and oxygen consumptions. The stack temperature is maintained at the value of the original plant at 150°C. Flue gas properties are reported in Table 27, the plant operating conditions and main assumptions are in Table 28, the plant mass, energy and CO₂ balance are in Table 29.

Table 27: Bio CHP plant flue gases at the stack

Flow rate	Nm ³ /h (0°C, 1 atm)	138'108
Mass flow rate	kg/s	49.83
T	°C	150.0
N ₂	%vol, wet basis	70.20%
O ₂	%vol, wet basis	5.0%
CO ₂	%vol, wet basis	13.05%
H ₂ O	%vol, wet basis	11.75%

Table 28: details of the CaL plant for Bio CHP application

Superheated steam temperature	°C	500
Superheated steam pressure	bar	60
Condensing type	-	Cooling towers
Condensation pressure	bar	0.086
F_0/F_{CO_2}	-	0.09
F_R/F_{CO_2}	-	7
Carbonator temperature	°C	650
Carbonator CO ₂ capture efficiency	%	89.36%
Carbonator SO ₂ capture efficiency	%	90%
Stack temperature	°C	150
Calcliner temperature	°C	920
Oxygen purity	%vol.	95%
Oxygen preheating temperature	°C	140
Oxygen concentration in oxidant gas	%	40%
Oxygen excess at calciner outlet	%vol, wet basis	3.50%
Temperature of the CO ₂ recirculation	°C	400
Cyclone efficiency on Ca particles	%	99.5%
Cyclone efficiency on ash particles	%	90%
Air infiltrations in the Reactors Heat Recovery Sections	%mass	1%
Air infiltration in bag filters	%mass	3%

Table 29: Main results of the mass and energy balance of the CaL-Bio CHP plant

Wood pellet (calcliner fuel) mass flow	t/h	17.36
Wood pellet power input	kW _{LHV}	88'503
Oxygen mass flow	t/h	26.60
Make-up mass flow	t/h	7.22
CO ₂ to storage	t/h	59.52
Electric power balance		
Steam turbine power	kW_e	28'619
Flue gas FD fan consumption	kW _e	951
Flue gas ID fan	kW _e	269
CO ₂ recirculation fan	kW _e	480
Condensate pump	kW _e	9
BFW pump	kW _e	248
Cooling Tower loop pump	kW _e	155
Cooling Tower fans	kW _e	200
ASU consumption	kW _e	6'303
CPU consumption	kW _e	8'495
Net electric power output	kW_e	11'510
CO₂ balance		
CO ₂ from Bio CHP	t/h	35.25
CO ₂ from RDF	t/h	30.82
CO ₂ from limestone calcination	t/h	3.17
Total CO₂ IN	t/h	69.25
CO ₂ to storage	t/h	59.52
CO ₂ to stack	t/h	3.75
CO ₂ in CPU off-gases	t/h	5.82
CO ₂ eq. in bag filter solids	t/h	0.16
Total CO₂ out	t/h	69.25

Figure 22: CaL plant application to Bio CHP process flow diagram

In Table 30 the technical KPIs of the WtE and Bio-CHP plants with CaL CO₂ capture are reported.

Table 30: technical KPIs of CaL applications to WtE and Bio CHP plants

		WtE+CaL	Bio-CHP+CaL
Overall Fuel consumption	t/y – TJ _{LHV} /y	1'092'000 – 13'500 ¹⁾	349'000 – 6'470 ¹⁾
Gross electric power	MW _e – MWh _e /y	153.6 – 1'229'000 ²⁾	72.0 – 576'000 ²⁾
Gross electric efficiency	%	32.76%	32.05%
Net electric power output	MW _e – MWh _e /y	98.12 – 785'000 ²⁾	50.6 – 405'000 ²⁾
Net electric efficiency	%	20.93%	22.52%
Carbonator CO ₂ capture efficiency	%	89.62%	89.4%
Direct CO ₂ emissions at stack	t/y – kg/t _{fuel}	197'000 – 281.4 ³⁻⁴⁾	76'600 – 364.4 ³⁻⁴⁾
Indirect CO ₂ emissions ¹⁾	t/y – kg/t _{fuel}	-271'900 – -388.4 ³⁻⁴⁾	-101'300 – -482.1 ³⁻⁴⁾
Equivalent CO ₂ emissions	t/y – kg/t _{fuel}	-74'900 – -107.0 ³⁻⁴⁾	-24'700 – -117.8 ³⁻⁴⁾
Net CO ₂ emissions	t/y – kg/t _{fuel}	-658'600 – -940.9 ⁴⁻⁵⁾	-577'500 – -2'748.2 ⁴⁻⁵⁾
CO ₂ avoided from flue gas	%	70.5%	72.8%
CCR (CO ₂ Capture Rate)	%	85.5%	86.2%
ΔP _e	MW _e – MWh _e /y	+ 28.1 – +225'000	+ 11.5 – +92'100
SPECCA	MJ _{LHV} /kg _{CO2}	5.32 ^{6.1)}	5.31 ^{6.2)}

¹⁾ indirect CO₂ emissions account for CO₂ emissions avoided from plant connected to the grid producing the same ΔP_e of the plant considered and not operating with CCS, that can be considered to be shut down due to the installation of the CaL retrofit. Emission factors have been considered as 1209 kg_{CO2}/MWh_e for the WtE case (burning the RDF sent to the calciner), and 1202 kg_{CO2}/MWh_e for the Bio CHP case (burning the wood pellet sent to the calciner).

¹⁾ includes both the thermal input from MSW for the WtE and the RDF for the calciner, the same holds for the Bio CHP (calciner and combustor both have wood pellet feed)

²⁾ includes the contributions from the steam turbines of both the WtE (or Bio CHP) and CaL

³⁾ includes the contributions of the share of CO₂ not captured by the carbonator and the CO₂ in the vent gases of the CPU.

⁴⁾ fuel specific quantities refer to the fuel burnt in the hosting plant (i.e. MSW or Wood pellet)

⁵⁾ net emissions account for the biogenic share of the carbon in the fuel and for indirect emissions. Biogenic CO₂ is considered to be climate neutral. Both plants reach carbon-negativity (sequester carbon from the atmosphere)

^{6.1)} taking as reference a WtE plant that generates electricity with a net electric efficiency of 28.8% (same as the one considered as host plant) and CO₂ emission factor of 1209 kg_{CO2}/MWh_e

^{6.2)} taking as reference a Biomass-fired plant that generates electricity with a net electric efficiency of 28.9% (same as the one considered as host plant) and CO₂ emission factor of 1202 kg_{CO2}/MWh_e

5.2.3 Steel application

The CaL plant applied to the EAF steelmaking process is depicted in Figure 23. Nonetheless, the fluctuating nature of EAF flue gas properties brings in some particular issues that should be taken into account for the configuration of the system. As a consequence, the CaL plant for the steel case incorporates a series of modifications/systems in order to reduce the impact of the varying flue gases properties on the performance of the system, which are listed below.

- The carbonator is adiabatic. That means that there is not heat extraction from the carbonator reactor. In this case, an external solid heat exchanger is used to cool down the solids from the calciner before entering the carbonator. In the external heat exchanger, heat is extracted from solids by heating up a molten salt stream and the outlet temperature of solids is adjusted for each case to have an overall carbonator temperature of 620°C.
- The ASU operation is decoupled from the calciner by implementing a tank to store liquid oxygen at 1.2 bar and -182°C (Hanak et al., 2017). The tank receives the oxygen produced by the ASU at a constant flow rate and provides the calciner with a variable flow rate according to the load, so the tank acts as a buffer between the ASU and the calciner. The advantages of this configuration are an ASU reduced size, since it is sized based on the average oxygen demand rather than the peak one, and a stable operation. On the other hand, producing liquid oxygen to be stored safely implies a higher ASU energy consumption. As a consequence, the ASU specific energy consumption for the application of CaL to steel case is assumed as 638 kWh/t_{O2} (Šulc and Ditzl, 2021).
- Similarly, a gas holder is included to store the rich-CO₂ gas resulting from the calciner at atmospheric pressure. The gas holder is placed between the water removal and the first compressor in the CPU (see Figure 18). This strategy allows to reduce the size of the CPU and limit its operation at off-design conditions; moreover, it is justified by the fact that large gas holders are common in the steel industry to store process gases.
- The sensible heat available from the CaL section is extracted with heat transfer fluids (HTF). Moreover, thermal energy storage (TES) tanks are placed between the CaL section and the power cycle to decouple their operation. Two different HTF were considered: molten salts (60 % NaNO₃, 40 % KNO₃) with operating temperatures within 265-550°C, and thermal oil Dowthermal A with operating temperature within 50- 290°C (Pan et al., 2018). The HTFs are heated up by exploiting the sensible energy in carbonator/calciner flue gases and the external solid heat exchanger. Then, the hot HTF are stored in dedicated tanks before going to the power block at a constant rate.

Figure 23: CaL plant application to EAF steelmaking process flow diagram.

The conditions of the CaL section at each load scenario are presented in Table 31, while clarification about the definition of such conditions is included below:

- The sizing of the CaL system is done considering scenario A as the design point, while the other scenarios (B-F) are analyzed as off-design cases of the system. As a result, the average gas velocities in the riser of the CFB carbonator and calciner are lower during off-design operation. Given the low gas velocities for cases C-F, it was assumed that the fluidization regime in the riser switches from fast to bubbling fluidization. It implies that during operation at bubbling fluidization regime, the solids to be recirculated between the reactor are extracted from the bottom of the risers.
- For the case F, given the very low flue gas flow rate, air is added to the carbonator in order to keep a minimum level of fluidization (gas velocity of 0.5 m/s). In addition, no CO₂ is captured in the carbonator due to the low CO₂ concentration in the gases, which is lower than the minimum CO₂ concentration limited by equilibrium.
- The carbonator temperature is set as 620°C (rather than the 650°C used in other cases) to improve the capture efficiency in the carbonator given the lower concentration of CO₂ in the flue gases (0.19 – 5.91%_{vol}). Furthermore, the carbonator temperature of 620°C is set for all the load scenarios at the expense of more fuel consumption in the calciner in order to limit the impact of fluctuations on the heat recovery section and attached steam power plant.

- For case A and B, F_R/F_{CO_2} and F_0/F_{CO_2} are defined to have a carbonator relative capture efficiency of 95%. For the other cases, given the reduced flue gases sensible heat (lower temperature and flow rate) and CO_2 concentration, higher F_R/F_{CO_2} and F_0/F_{CO_2} are fix so that hot solids from the calciner provide the thermal energy required to have the carbonator temperature of 620°C.

Each case is simulated assuming quasi-steady state operation and technical and economic KPIs are calculated for each case. The results from the six steady state simulations are used to interpolate the corresponding KPIs for each of the operating condition according to the profiles reported in Figure 4. This implies to main assumptions: **i)** A linear evolution of the KPIs between each couple of points (for example, between case A and B, B and C, etc.), and **ii)** the system is able to adapt to each operating point instantaneously and its dynamic response is not considered for the definition of the base KPIs.

Table 31: Parameters of CaL section for each condition simulated for the EAF plant case.

		A	B	C	D	E	F
Reactors fluidization regime	-	Fast	Fast	Bubbling	Bubbling	Bubbling	Bubbling
F_0/F_{CO_2}	-	6.25	6.25	9.80	22.00	42.20	2492.00
F_R/F_{CO_2}	-	0.10	0.10	0.08	0.20	0.30	80.00
Carbonator temperature	°C	620	620	620	620	620	620
Carbonator CO_2 capture efficiency	%	87.48	87.20	84.96	75.76	67.50	0.00
Carbonator average gas velocity	m/s	5.00	3.89	2.62	1.28	0.50	0.50
Calciner average gas velocity	m/s	5.00	2.95	1.91	0.98	0.50	0.73
Calciner temperature	°C	920	920	920	920	920	920
Oxygen purity	%	95	95	95	95	95	95
Oxygen preheating temperature	°C	150	150	150	150	150	150
Oxygen concentration in oxidant gas	%	40	40	40	40	40	40
Oxygen excess at calciner outlet	%vol, wet basis	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Temperature of the CO_2 recirculation	°C	400	400	400	400	400	400
Cyclone efficiency on Ca particles	%	99.5	99.5	99.5	99.5	99.5	99.5
Cyclone efficiency on ash particles	%	90.0	90.0	90.0	90.0	90.0	90.0

Given the local availability of waste biomass from forest industry in the area where the EAF plant is located (North Europe), waste biomass is used as the fuel for the calciner, whose properties are included in Table 32. Moreover, using waste biomass as the fuel for the calciner could lead to negative emissions from the process since the CO_2 from biomass combustion is considered biogenic.

Table 32: Properties of waste biomass used as fuel in the calciner in the CaL plant applied to the EAD plant (Saeed et al., 2023).

Proximate analysis		
Volatile matter	%wt – dry basis	74.10
Fixed carbon	%wt – dry basis	21.85
Ash	%wt – dry basis	4.05
Ultimate analysis		
C	%wt – dry basis	51.00
H	%wt – dry basis	5.80
N	%wt – dry basis	0.90
O	%wt – dry basis	38.21
S	%wt – dry basis	0.04
Ash	%wt – dry basis	4.05
Moisture ^a	%wt – wet basis	10.00

^{a)} The 10% moisture content is assumed considering the waste biomass comes from the milling process (Gayan et al., 2004).

The mass flow of fuel, oxygen, make-up (limestone), and CaL CO₂ balance for each case are included in Table 33, while, the average mass and energy balances for the CaL system applied to the EAF plant are presented in Table 34. Moreover, the technical KPIs of the EAF + CaL system are presented in Table 35. The low net electric power output from the integrated system (0.4 MWe) is due mainly to the high electricity demand of the ASU to produce liquid oxygen of 638 kWh/t_{O₂} (Šulc and Ditl, 2021).

Table 33: CaL plant application to EAF principal boundary material and energy streams for each case.

		A	B	C	D	E	F
Calciner fuel (biomass) demand	t/h	19.64	11.73	7.66	3.97	1.74	2.15
Calciner oxygen demand	t/h	29.18	17.43	11.29	5.79	2.53	3.11
Make-up mass flow	t/h	8.06	4.82	1.83	0.65	1.94	0.85
CO₂ balance							
CO ₂ from EAF off-gas	t/h	35.44	21.21	10.04	2.88	0.85	0.02
CO ₂ from limestone calcination	t/h	3.54	2.12	0.80	0.29	0.26	0.37
CO ₂ from biomass fuel	t/h	33.03	19.73	12.89	6.68	2.92	3.61
Total CO₂ IN	t/h	72.01	43.06	23.73	9.84	4.03	4.01
CO ₂ in carbonator vent gas	t/h	4.44	2.71	1.51	0.70	0.28	0.04
CO ₂ eq. in bag filter solids	t/h	0.16	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
CO ₂ to CPU gas holder	t/h	67.42	40.25	22.22	9.14	3.75	3.98
Total CO₂ OUT	t/h	72.01	43.05	23.73	9.84	4.03	4.01

Table 34: Average results of the mass and energy balance of the CaL-EAF plant.

Calciner fuel (biomass) mass flow	t/h	7.51
Biomass power input	kW _{LHV}	33'831
Oxygen mass flow	t/h	11.10
Make-up mass flow	t/h	2.76
CO ₂ to storage	t/h	21.17
Electric power balance		
Power block net power output	kW_e	12'708
EAF off-gas fan consumption	kW _e	475
Flue gas stack ID fan	kW _e	1'182
CO ₂ recirculation fan	kW _e	199
ASU consumption	kW _e	7'080
CPU consumption	kW _e	3'372
Net electric power output	kW_e	400

Table 35: Technical KPIs of CaL application to the EAF plant.

Indicator	Units	Value
Overall Fuel consumption	t/y – TJ _{LHV} /y	60'071 – 974 ¹⁾
Net electric power from the power cycle	MW _e – MWh _e /y	12.71 – 101'680 ²⁾
Net electric efficiency of the power cycle	%	37.56%
Net electric power output	MW _e – MWh _e /y	0.40 – 3'206 ³⁾
Net electric efficiency	%	1.18%
Carbonator CO ₂ capture efficiency	%	85.70%
Direct specific primary energy consumption	MJ/kg _{steel}	0.30 ¹⁾
Indirect specific primary energy consumption	MJ/kg _{steel}	3.73 ⁴⁾
Equivalent specific primary energy consumption	MJ/kg _{steel}	4.04
Direct CO ₂ emissions at stack	t/y – kg/kg _{steel}	21'504 – 0.024 ⁴⁾
Indirect CO ₂ emissions ¹⁾	t/y – kg/kg _{steel}	126'336 – 0.141
Equivalent CO ₂ emissions	t/y – kg/kg _{steel}	147'840 – 0.165
Net CO ₂ emissions	t/y – kg/kg _{steel}	-793'312 – -0.089 ⁵⁾
CO ₂ avoided from flue gas	%	82.00
CCR (CO ₂ Capture Rate)	%	89.07 ⁶⁾
SPECCA	MJ _{LHV} /kg _{CO2}	2.75 ⁷⁾

¹⁾ indirect CO₂ emissions account for CO₂ emissions related to the electricity consumed by the EAF, considering it is produced in a power plant with an efficiency of 51.3% (EU-27 electrical efficiency) and specific emission factor of 265 kg_{CO2}/MWh_e. A average value of 60 MW was considered as the electricity consumption in the EAF (see Table 11)

¹⁾ refers only to the fuel input to the CaL system (biomass burned in the calciner).

²⁾ this is the net power produced by the power cycle. Part of this power is consumed by plant components such as CPU, ASU, and gas fans.

³⁾ net electric power output from the CaL system after ASU, CPU and fans consumption.

⁴⁾ includes the contributions of the share of CO₂ not captured by the carbonator and the CO₂ in the vent gases of the CPU.

⁵⁾ net emissions account for the biogenic share of the carbon in the fuel (biomass) and for direct emissions. Biogenic CO₂ is assumed to be climate neutral. The integrated EAF – CaL plant reaches carbon-negativity (sequester carbon from the atmosphere).

⁶⁾ it is captured considering the CO₂ captured from the EAF flue gases and the fuel burnt in the calciner.

⁷⁾ taking as reference a EAF plant producing 112 t_{steel}/h (same as the one considered as host plant) and CO₂ emission factor of 242 kg_{CO2}/t_{steel}.

5.3 Economic analysis

5.3.1 Cement application

From an economic point of view, configuration CFB-CaL Limestone 50%-CaLSR shows a TPC of about 280.1 M€, which is about 15% lower than configuration CFB-CaL Raw Meal 50%-CaLSR, resulting in a TPC of 322.8 M€. This is mainly due to the reduction of ASU and CPU sizes in configuration using limestone, compared to configuration using raw meal. In fact, the cost of these two items accounts for about 50% of the TPC. Figure 24 shows the breakdown of the total plant cost for both configurations considered in this deliverable.

Figure 24: Total Plant Cost break-down for CaL application to cement plant (top: CFB-CaL Limestone 50%-CaLSR; bottom: CFB-CaL Raw Meal 50%-CaLSR). In dark blue (exploded), the Total Installed Cost.

Table 36 reports the breakdown of the cost of CO₂ avoided (CCA) for both cases considered in this deliverable.

Table 36: Breakdown of the cost of CO₂ avoided (CCA) for both CFB-CaL cement plants considered in this work.

		Cement plant with CFB-CaL Limestone 50%-CaLSR	Cement plant with CFB-CaL Raw Meal 50%-CaLSR
Fuel (coal)	€/t _{CO2}	6.77	10.41
Electricity	€/t _{CO2}	11.83	7.91
Other variable costs (incl. CO ₂ transport and storage)	€/t _{CO2}	18.63	22.77
Total Variable OPEX	€/t_{CO2}	37.23	41.09
Fixed OPEX	€/t_{CO2}	20.05	22.99
CAPEX	€/t_{CO2}	35.06	40.54
Cost of CO₂ avoided	€/t_{CO2}	92.34	104.63

In addition to the energy considerations already presented in section 5.2.1, also from an economic point of view, the case with limestone as CO₂-sorbent turns out to be better than the case using raw meal as CO₂-sorbent, thanks to the reduction in CAPEX, reduction in the variable cost associated with fuel, and reduction in the costs associated with CO₂ transport and storage (because of less CO₂ is generated in the calciner). This results in lower CCA of the case with limestone (92.3 €/t_{CO2}) compared with the case with raw meal (104.6 €/t_{CO2}). Regarding the increase in clinker production cost (considering a carbon tax of 80 €/t_{CO2}), the case with raw meal shows an increase in production cost of about 21.9 €/t_{clk}, while the case with limestone shows a lower increase in production cost of about 8.6 €/t_{clk}. Figure 25 shows the breakdown of the increase in cost of clinker for CFB-CaL Limestone 50%-CaLSR (Figure 25-left) and CFB-CaL Raw Meal 50%-CaLSR (Figure 25-right) cases.

Figure 25: Cost breakdown for clinker cost increment for CFB-CaL Limestone 50%-CaLSR case (left) and CFB-CaL Raw Meal 50%-CaLSR case (right).

5.3.2 Waste to Energy and Bio-CHP applications

For the **WtE application** it is assumed to employ RDF as the fuel for the calciner, and its cost is assumed to be 20 €/t_{RDF}, limestone cost is assumed as 15 €/t_{CaCO3} (Astolfi et al., 2019). Following the assumptions in section 3.2, and given the fact that the CO₂ emissions of the integrated plant (WtE+CaL) are lower than the fossil CO₂ emissions of the WtE plant, it is assumed that all CO₂ emissions are of biogenic origin and, therefore, not subjected to pay any carbon tax. Moreover, the fossil CO₂ emissions captured from the WtE flue gases are preventing the plant to pay the corresponding carbon tax, and so the their capture effect is equivalent to a cash flow corresponding to the carbon tax price. The capture of the biogenic share of the CO₂ present in the WtE flue gases and generated in the combustion process of the RDF, is supposed to be valorized at the price of the carbon tax (i.e. the plant is generating carbon credits due to emissions negative on an atmosphere CO₂ balance). The Total Plant Cost has been estimated in 493.6 M€ and is divided as in Figure 26. As a result of this and all of the other assumptions in section 3.2, the break-even gate-fee increment is computed in 33.6 €/t of MSW (Figure 27-left).

Similarly, maintaining the same gate-fee at the present value (no gate-fee increment), the CCA (Cost of CO₂ Avoided) results in 112.7 €/t_{CO2} (Figure 27-right).

Figure 26: Total Plant Cost break-down for CaL application to WtE plant. In dark blue (exploded), the Total Installed Cost (sum of costs of the equipment once installed and connected together).

Figure 27: Cost breakdown for the break-even gate fee increment (left), and for the Cost of CO₂ Avoided (right), this latter is computed taking into account the fact that the WtE+CaL plant is reaching negative net emissions due to the biogenic carbon content in the MSW and RDF.

For the **Bio CHP application** it is assumed to employ Wood Pellet as the fuel for the calciner, the same employed as the fuel for the main boiler, and its cost is assumed to be 40 €/t_{WP} and as for the WtE application case, the limestone cost is assumed as 15 €/t_{limestone}. As stated before, given the biogenic origin of the CO₂ generated in the combustion of the main fuel and the fuel of the calciner, the CO₂ captured and sent to storage is foreseen to be valorized at the price of the carbon tax (i.e. the plant is generating carbon credits due to emissions negative on an atmosphere CO₂ balance). The Total Plant Cost has been estimated in 290.0 M€ and is divided as in Figure 28. As a result of this and all of the other assumptions in chapter 3.2, the break-even electricity sale price (in case of full-electric configuration) is computed in 29.0 €/MWh_e (Figure 29-left). The cost of CO₂ avoided is 104.1 €/t_{CO2} (Figure 29-right).

Figure 28: Total Plant Cost break-down for CaL application to Bio CHP plant. In dark blue (exploded), the Total Installed Cost (sum of costs of the equipment once installed and connected together).

Figure 29: Cost breakdown for the break-even electricity price increment (left), and for the Cost of CO₂ Avoided (right), this latter is computed taking into account the fact that the Bio CHP+CaL plant is reaching negative net emissions due to the biogenic carbon content in the fuel of the main boiler and of the calciner.

5.3.3 Steel application

For the **EAF application** it is assumed to employ residual biomass as the fuel for the calciner, and its cost is assumed to be 55 €/t (Basile et al., 2022); limestone cost is assumed as 15 €/t_{CaCO₃} (Astolfi et al., 2019). Similar to the WtE and Bio-CHP applications, it is assumed that all CO₂ emissions from the EAF + CaL are of biogenic origin and, therefore, not subjected to pay any carbon tax. Moreover, the fossil CO₂ emissions captured from the EAF off-gases are preventing the plant from paying the corresponding carbon tax, and so their capture effect is equivalent to a cash

flow corresponding to the carbon tax price. Furthermore, the CO₂ from the biomass combustion in the calciner is supposed to be valued at the price of the carbon tax (i.e. the plant is generating carbon credits due to emissions negative on an atmosphere CO₂ balance). The Total Plant Cost has been estimated in 290.43 M€ and is divided as in Figure 30. The costs of the ASU and CPU (including their storages) represent about 44% of the total installed cost, which is consistent with the typical share of these components (~50%) in the CAPEX of the CaL system. These results suggest that the reduction in the cost of the ASU and CPU are compensated by the cost of the storing vessels. This is particularly relevant for the CPU system, where gas storage accounts for about 30% of the total cost. Besides, the low share of the reactors (5%) in the total installed cost resulted from the fact that an adiabatic carbonator was considered, and so it does not include the internal heat recovery components. The cost of the external solid heat exchanger controlling the temperature of solid entering the carbonator is included in the "Heat recovery sections" category.

As a result of this and all of the other assumptions in section 3.2, the steel cost increment is computed in 39.36 €/t of steel (Figure 31-left). Similarly, if no steel cost increment is assumed, the Cost of CO₂ avoided (CCA) should be 288.6 €/t_{steel} (Figure 31-right). This figures are highly impacted by the low net power output of the CaL plant (0.4 MW) due to the high electricity consumption by the ASU to produce liquid oxygen.

Figure 30: Total Plant Cost break-down for CaL application to EAF plant. In dark blue (exploded), the Total Installed Cost (sum of costs of the equipment once installed and connected together).

Figure 31: Cost breakdown for steel cost increment (left), and for the Cost of CO₂ Avoided (right), this latter is computed taking into account the fact that the EAF+CaL plant is reaching negative net emissions due to the biogenic carbon content in the biomass used as fuel in the calciner.

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